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МАДАНИЯТ ВА САЊАТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ КУЛЬТУРА И ИСКУССТВО | JOURNAL OF CULTURE AND ART

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PECULIARITIES OF PERFORMANCE OF THE CLASSICAL ERA CHAMBER SONATAS USING THE EXAMPLE OF “SONATA FOR VIOLIN AND PIANO NO. 4” BY L.V. BEETHOVEN

ANNOTATION

This article is devoted to the chamber music of L.V. Beethoven using the example of “Sonata for Violin and Piano No. 4”. The author's violin sonatas occupy an important place in the performing and teaching activities of musicians. L.V. Beethoven made an invaluable contribution to the development of chamber music. His chamber works are masterpieces of musical art. Based on performing experience, the author reveals the stylistic features and artistic images in this work.

Keywords: Chamber music, violin, piano, sonata, form, thematic theme, genre, performance aspects.

СКРИПКА УЧУН SONATA МИСОЛИДА КЛАССИК ДАВР ПАЛАТАСИ СОНАТАЛАРИНИ ИЖРО ЕТИШНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ ПИАНИНО № 4 Л. V. БЕТХОВЕН ТОМОНИДАН

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақола Л. V. Бетховеннинг “№ 4-скрипка ва пианино учун Sonata” мисолидан фойдаланган ҳолда камера музикасига бағишланган. Муаллифнинг скрипка сонаталари музикачиларнинг ижрочилик ва ўқитувчилик фаолиятида муҳим ўрин тутди. Л. V. Бетховен камера музикаси ривожига бебаҳо ҳисса қўшди. Унинг камера асарлари музика санъатининг дурдоналаридир. Ижрочилик тажрибасига асосланиб, муаллиф ушбу асардаги стилистик хусусиятлар ва бадиий образларни очиб беради.

Калит сўзлар: камера музикаси, скрипка, фортепиано, sonata, шакл, тематик мавзу, жанр, ижро жиҳатлари.

ОСОБЕННОСТИ ИСПОЛНЕНИЯ КАМЕРНЫХ СОНАТ ЭПОХИ КЛАССИЦИЗМА НА ПРИМЕРЕ “СОНАТЫ ДЛЯ СКРИПКИ И ФОРТЕПИАНО № 4” Л.В. БЕТХОВЕНА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Данная статья посвящена камерной музыке Л.В. Бетховена на примере “Сонаты для скрипки и фортепиано № 4”. Скрипичные сонаты автора занимают важное место в исполнительской и преподавательской деятельности музыкантов. Л.В. Бетховен внес неоценимый вклад в развитие камерной музыки. Его камерные произведения являются шедеврами музыкального искусства. Основываясь на исполнительском опыте, автор раскрывает стилистические особенности и художественные образы в этом произведении.

Ключевые слова: камерная музыка, скрипка, фортепиано, соната, форма, тематическая тема, жанр, аспекты исполнения.

Teaching the “Chamber Ensemble” discipline includes many aspects and nuances. The program of this subject in higher educational institutions consists of several stages. It is built on the principle of developing technical skills - from simple to complicated. It is obligatory to study chamber works of different eras - classicism, romanticism, modernity. At the first stages of training, it is advisable to study chamber works by composers of the classical era - J. Haydn, W. A. Mozart and L. V. Beethoven, since the material to study is technically simple and musically understandable for students. Clarity of composition, construction of phrases, simplicity of form - makes it easier for students to understand the basic concepts and rules of playing in a chamber ensemble. Sonatas of the classical period cultivate the unity of rhythm, strokes, agogics, the ability to hear a partner and oneself as part of the ensemble [1, 2].

In this article we will examine the study of chamber works of the classical era using the example of L. V. Beethoven's sonata for violin and piano.

Ludwig van Beethoven is a German composer, one of the representatives of the Vienna School. The composer's chamber music is very extensive. These are sonatas, trios, variations, quartets and quintets. Most often, sonatas for violin and piano are performed in the chamber ensemble class. The composer wrote 10 sonatas for these instruments.

Most of Beethoven's violin Sonatas (from the First to the Eighth) were created in his early period of work. However, they are extremely diverse and deeply original in style and perfect in execution. Already in the first violin sonatas, Beethoven breaks with the established tradition of the *divertissement-suite*: his sonata *allegro* are single-minded, full of active action, the slow movements are deep and “Schubertian” songlike. It is not surprising that they began to select words for the melodious *Adagio* and *Andante* sonatas and sing them in everyday life and in concerts (just like later instrumental pieces by Chopin, Liszt, Rubinstein). Often the composer uses his favorite variation form. In the finales - usually in the form of a rondo - genre scenes come to life, and the element of dance reigns.

Violin sonatas are very diverse in mood and content. Technically, they are also very different. Therefore, at the first stages of studying sonatas in universities, we mainly perform the Second and Fourth Sonatas for violin and piano, since they are simpler for first- and second-year students.

Let us focus on a detailed study and analysis of the Sonata for Violin and Piano No. 4.

The Sonata for Violin and Piano in A minor, Op 23, was created by the composer in 1801 and dedicated to Count Moritz von Fries, a wealthy art collector and philanthropist [3].

This sonata is very unusual both for listeners and for the composer himself. This is the first sonata in a minor key of its time. Chamber music was considered a “light genre”, music for relaxation and entertainment and did not imply any drama. Therefore, composers of that period wrote sonatas only in major keys. The minor sonata is a very rare exception for that time; in this way the composer emphasizes the exceptional seriousness of the content. Beethoven strengthens this figurative focus - not only the first part is written in a minor key, but also the final one. Between them is a slow major part.

The first part - Presto.

The first part is very dramatic, in a minor key, and differs from the first three sonatas in character, minor mood and tragedy. However, it is more concise and smaller in volume. Character – impetuous, calling for action [4].

The image shows a page of musical notation for the first movement of Beethoven's Sonata No. 2 in E minor, Op. 2, No. 1. The score is in 4/4 time and marked 'Presto'. It features a piano part (left hand) and a violin part (right hand). The piano part begins with a forte piano (fp) dynamic and a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes. The violin part begins with a forte piano (fp) dynamic and a melodic line. The score includes various dynamics such as sf, f, and cresc. (crescendo).

The peculiarity of the structure of the texture is very important. Both parts - the piano and the violin - constitute two equal elements, forming a single musical image. Therefore, each of the performers must show their theme very clearly.

The side part in E minor presents a calmer image. But in all voices, there is a tireless movement, like an invisible struggle within thematics. The polyphonic interweaving of the voices of violin and piano enhances the impression. Chromatic intonation reminds us of the tragedy of the first movement.

The development begins with the main theme in D minor. The constant exchange of calls between the piano and the violin is a moment of competition between the two instruments. Everything comes to the lyrical theme of the violin in F major. The piano accompanies, repeating the same motive. Afterwards a dramatic moment appears, the caustic sforzandos return. The interplay between instruments gains momentum and leads to a vibrant fortissimo climax.

Before the reprise, a new thematic theme appears in development. This is an excited violin melody with chromatic intonations and a lyrical tone. Piano intercepts the melody and carries out the theme. Gradually growing, the melody leads to a reprise.

The second Part - Andante scherzoso, piu allegretto.

The theme of part 2 is based on a light and relaxed melody, very light, lively, filled with air - pauses. The theme begins at the piano, cautiously, as if spoken in a whisper. Constant off-beat intonations give the feeling of sighs. Expressive pauses seem to be filled with the sound of an echo. The violin picks up the theme and there is a rollcall between the instruments.

Andante scherzoso, più Allegretto.

Andante scherzoso, più Allegretto.

p

The connecting party is more mobile in nature. The theme is constructed in the form of a fugato - a favorite technique in Beethoven's sonatas.

A

p

tr.

cresc.

tr.

cresc.

tr.

tr.

Even more unique is the playful side game. Looks like a Mozart-style tongue twister.

The final part is more legate, touchingly tender - another image of Mozart's sonatas. The development of the second part is small, not filled with drama, built on the themes of the main and secondary parts. The reprise differs from the exposition by the scherzo character in the violin part.

The third part - Allegro molto.

The finale of the sonata is written in the form of a rondo. The refrain is full of drama and epicness. The theme is very fast-paced, excited, directed upward. Against the background of the violin's cut point, which is written in syncopation, which gives a more excited character, the piano's theme sounds in a piano tone, with the exception of the climax - a small sforzando. And then again a sharp decline on piano [5].

The second episode is major, light, chord texture for the piano and response notes for the violin. The roll call between the two instruments seems to go upward, and then freezes again on the fermata.

The most striking episode is the climax in the 3rd movement of the sonata. This is a bright, fast-paced theme for the forte piano - figurations built on arpeggios and bright chords for the violin. The piano then picks up the chords and the violin plays an arpeggio. Bright sforzandos on the piano chords lead to an opening chord that freezes on the fermata. Performers are required to accurately convey thematic themes from one instrument to another. That is, the ability to complement each other, imitate strokes, timbre, dynamics and agogy.

At the conclusion of the sonata there is an octave refrain at the piano. A bright, rich, emotional theme completes the sonata.

The pronounced romantic character of L. V. Beethoven's "Fourth Sonata for Violin and Piano" attracts many outstanding musicians and is interpreted by them in different ways.

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